

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY INVESTIGATION OF SPACE WEATHERING OF APOLLO ROCK SAMPLES. K. M. Peters¹, E. A. Cloutis¹, D. M. Applin¹, T. M. Ledoux¹, S. C. Lambert¹, and D. Das¹ ¹Centre for Terrestrial and Planetary Exploration (C-TAPE), University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Avenue, Winnipeg, Manitoba, Canada R3B 2E9 (peters-k98@webmail.uwinnipeg.ca).

Introduction: The Moon, being an airless body, experiences space weathering from such things as solar wind irradiation and micrometeoroid bombardment. This leads to a variety of physical and chemical alterations of lunar soils and rocks [1]. Moreover, these alterations affect the spectral and compositional properties of lunar materials. To aid future lunar exploration, we have spectrally characterized a suite of Apollo rock samples using Raman spectroscopy.

These samples were collected from the Moon's surface by Apollo astronauts. The samples were selected to enable spectroscopic characterization of a space-exposed surface, as well as an interior. We received chips of the upper and lower surfaces from three rocks from NASA's Astromaterials Facility (Table 1).

We have spectrally characterized these rock chips using a Raman spectrometer, to understand space weathering on rocks.

Methods: A BWTek i-Raman spectrometer was used to collect Raman spectra from 175-4000 Δcm^{-1} , using a 532 nm laser, and a spectral resolution of $\sim 4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Spot size of each measurement is ~ 85 microns. Ten Raman spectra were collected on each rock face in order to capture any spectral variability.

Table 1. Apollo rock samples included in this study.

Generic	Specific	Parent	Apollo Mission
15555	859	47	Apollo 15
15555	1117	465	Apollo 15
65015	323	15	Apollo 16
65015	326	25	Apollo 16
71175	48	0	Apollo 17
71175	50	0	Apollo 17

Sample Descriptions: The samples selected in this study represent a well-studied Apollo 15 rock, 15555, and two rocks, one from Apollo 16 and another from Apollo 17, as a part of these two latter rocks had been buried within the lunar surface. Having been buried, the exposed face of the rock would experience far greater degrees of space weathering, whereas the covered portion of the rock would experience less or no space weathering.

Apollo sample 15555 is one of the largest samples collected and returned from the Moon. It is representative of the basaltic terrains of the Apollo 15 landing site. It is a coarse grained, porphyritic rock with olivine and pyroxene phenocrysts in a plagioclase matrix. Its mineralogy consists of olivine, pyroxene, plagioclase, spinel, and silica [2].

Sample 65015 was half buried in the regolith of the lunar surface, making it an ideal candidate to explore space weathering effects. It is an impact melt rock, containing olivine, pyroxene, plagioclase, whitlockite, and metals [3].

Sample 71175 was partially buried and has not yet been adequately studied. Being basaltic, it has long crystals of plagioclase intergrown with pyroxene, and ilmenite grains scattered throughout [4].

Figure 1: Raman spectra of Apollo chip 65015.323.

Figure 2: A portion of Fig 1. Raman spectra isolated to show pyroxene peaks in the $\sim 673 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and the $\sim 999 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region.

Discussion: Space weathering can be caused by many factors, such as impact-induced metamorphism and microparticle flux, causing melting, vaporization and regolith gardening, solar flares and solar wind. These factors can cause the breaking of molecular bonds, amorphization, and forming of nanophase iron. Lunar samples that have been irradiated in the laboratory show reduced reflectance and redder spectral slopes compared to non-irradiated samples. Such kinds of irradiation can promote the formation of nanophase iron, which is concentrated on the surfaces of Fe-bearing silicates [5].

In Figures 1 and 2, we present Raman spectra on Apollo chip 65015.323. Mineral phases detected are pyroxene around $\sim 673\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 999\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and possible plagioclase signatures may be hidden due to Raman artifacts from fibre optics around the 300-500 cm^{-1} region. The overall intensity of our Raman spectra is very low, possibly pointing towards exposure to space weathering [1, 6].

Conclusion: This study on Apollo rocks will provide valuable insight into space weathering as it relates to Raman spectroscopy. The information found within this study will aid future and current lunar rover missions.

Figure 3: Image of Apollo rock 15555. (AS15-82-11164)

References: [1] Lu, X. et al. (2025). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 130(5). [2] www.lpi.usra.edu/lunar/samples/atlas/compendium/15555r.pdf. [3] www.lpi.usra.edu/lunar/samples/atlas/compendium/65015.pdf. [4] www.lpi.usra.edu/lunar/samples/atlas/compendium/71175.pdf. [5] Weber, I. et al., (2022). *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy*, 53(3), 411-419. [6] Xu, J., et al. (2023). *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 672, A115.